

A new species of *Fusinus* (Gastropoda: Fascioliariidae) from East Australia

Una nueva especie de *Fusinus* (Gastropoda: Fascioliariidae) del este de Australia

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ABSTRACT

Fusinus palmarium is described from off East Australia, between Queensland and New South Wales, in 210-405 m depth. The new species is distinguished by its shell morphology from all other Australian *Fusinus* species and is compared to a few of them.

RESUMEN

Se describe la especie *Fusinus palmarium* del este de Australia, entre Queensland y Nueva Gales del Sur, a 210-405 m de profundidad. La nueva especie se distingue del resto de los *Fusinus* australianos por la morfología de la concha, se compara con dos de estas especies.

KEY WORDS: Mollusca, Gastropoda, Fascioliariidae, *Fusinus*, new species, East Australia, Queensland, New South Wales.

Palabras clave: Mollusca, Gastropoda, Fascioliariidae, *Fusinus*, nueva especie, Este de Australia, Queensland, Nueva Gales del Sur.

INTRODUCTION

Several *Fusinus* species have been described from Australian waters during the last years: HADORN AND FRAUSSEN (2003: 236, 238) described *F. westralis*, an endemic species from Western Australia, in the subgenus *Chryseofusus*. SNYDER (2004: 123-130) recently described two endemic Western Australian species, *F. wellsi* Snyder, 2004 and *F. vercoi* Snyder, 2004. *F. palmarium* sp. nov. seems to be endemic to eastern Australia.

A first lot was obtained during a routine NSW Fisheries cruise, collected by the Fisheries biologist K. J. Graham on the FRV "Kapala". A second lot was collected by the HMAS "Kimbla", a

naval ship which was used as a research platform, during an Australian Museum cruise led by W. F. Ponder for general shelf and slope sampling. A third lot was trawled by a fishing boat on the edge of the shelf outside the Swain Reefs. Alan Limpus obtained the molluscan by-catch and donated this material to the Australian Museum. The studied material is housed in the Australian Museum, Sydney (AMS).

Abbreviations used:

AMS Australian Museum, Sydney, Australia

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MNHN Muséum national d'Histoire
naturelle, Paris, France
RH Collection of Roland Hadorn, Lyss,
Switzerland

QM Queensland Museum, Brisbane,
Australia
dd dead collected specimen; juv juvenile
specimen; lv live collected specimen

SYSTEMATICS

Family FASCIOLARIIDAE Gray, 1853
Subfamily FUSININAE Wrigley, 1927
Genus *Fusinus* Rafinesque, 1815

Type species: *Murex colus* Linnaeus, 1758, by monotypy. Recent, Indo-Pacific.

Fusinus (Fusinus) palmarium sp. nov. (Figs. 1-6)

Type material: Holotype AMS C.422362 (37.1 x 12.4 mm, dd). – Paratype 1 QM Mo.78450 (39.8 x 12.5 mm, dd). – Paratype 2 MNHN (37.1 x 12.0 mm, dd). – Paratype 3 RH (38.4 x 12.5 mm, dd). Holotype and all paratypes from Australia, Queensland, Great Barrier Reef, off Swain Reefs, off Hixson Cay, 22° 33' S, 153° 26' E, 216-227 m.

Other material examined: Australia, New South Wales, southeast of Clarence River, KAPALA stn K75-9-4, 29° 41' S to 29° 32' S, 153° 45' E to 153° 47' E, 405-412 m, 1 dd, AMS C.312956. – Queensland, off Fraser Island, KIMBLA stn 27, 24° 57.9' S, 153° 37.3' E, 210 m, 1 lv juv, AMS C.422354. – Queensland, Great Barrier Reef, off Swain Reefs, off Hixson Cay, 22° 33' S, 153° 26' E, 216-227 m, 5 dd, AMS C.456842 (ex. AMS C.422362).

Type locality: Australia, Queensland, Great Barrier Reef, off Swain Reefs, off Hixson Cay, 22° 33' S, 153° 26' E, 216-227 m.

Etymology: *Fusinus palmarium* sp. nov. is derived from palmarium (Latin, neutrum) meaning “a masterpiece” which refers to the beautiful sculpture and white colour.

Description: Shell rather small for the genus (37.0-41.1 mm in length), fusiform, with elongate, pointed spire and long, almost straight siphonal canal, uniform white. Spire consisting of 8^{1/2}-9^{1/2} convex whorls including protoconch. Upper whorls convex, latter whorls carinated below middle of whorl, subsutural slope broad, straight. Suture distinct, constricted. Fine axial growth lines well-visible on all teleoconch whorls.

Protoconch white, bulbous, glossy, consisting of 1^{1/4}-1^{1/2} convex whorls. Final part (1/4 whorl) ornamented with 3 strong, widely spaced axial riblets reaching from suture to suture, transition to teleoconch abrupt, marked by a fine varix. Diameter 0.7-0.8 mm.

Axial sculpture consisting of strong, broad axial ribs, running from suture to suture on upper whorls, becoming more prominent at periphery, slightly withdrawing from upper suture on penultimate or body whorl. Interspaces rela-

tively deep, as broad as ribs, occasionally slightly broader. 6-8 axial ribs on upper postnuclear whorls, 7-9 on penultimate and 7-10 on body whorl.

Teleoconch beginning with 4 or 5 primary spiral cords, 5 on the latter whorls. From second or third teleoconch whorl on, one fine intercalated secondary spiral cord appearing between primary cords. Tertiary cords appearing from fourth whorl on at both sides of the slightly stronger secondary cords, their number increasing up to 2 on body whorl. Cords strong and sharp when crossing axial ribs, 3 abapical ones more prominent, peripheral one strongest.

Aperture roundly-ovate, white, rather small, pointed above, suddenly constricted below. Outer lip thick, strongly convex, edge slightly crenulated, with up to 15 fine indistinct internal lirae. Inner lip slightly calloused, smooth, attached to parietal wall. Siphonal canal straight, long, narrow, tapering anteriorly.

Figures 1-6. *Fusinus palmarium* sp. nov. 1, 2: holotype AMS C.422362, Queensland, Great Barrier Reef, off Hixson Cay, 37.1 mm; 3, 4: paratype 1 QM Mo.78450, same locality, 39.8 mm; 5, 6: paratype 3 RH, same locality, 38.4 mm.

Figuras 1-6. Fusinus palmarium sp. nov. 1, 2: holotipo AMS C.422362, Queensland, Arrecife de la Gran Barrera, frente a Hixson Cay, 37,1 mm; 3, 4: paratipo 1 QM Mo.78450, misma localidad, 39,8 mm; 5, 6: paratipo 3 RH, misma localidad, 38,4 mm.

Operculum typical of genus, light brown, filling the aperture. Periostracum unknown.

Range and habitat: East Australia, from Queensland (Swain Reefs) to New South Wales (southeast of Clarence

River). Empty shells 227-405 m deep, one live collected specimen 210 m deep on coarse calcareous nodules.

Comparison: None of the known Australian *Fusinus* is similar to the new species. *Fusinus annae* Snyder, 1986, *F.*

australis (Quoy and Gaimard, 1833), *F. colus* (Linnaeus, 1758), *F. nicobaricus* (Röding, 1798), *F. novaehollandiae* (Reeve, 1848), *F. salisburyi* Fulton, 1930, and *F. undatus* (Gmelin, 1791), all well illustrated in WILSON (1994: 68-69, pl. 13), are distinguished by a much larger adult size and a different shape. The recently described species *F. wellsii* Snyder, 2004 and *F. vercoi* Snyder, 2004 from Western Australia differ by having a larger adult size and by the wider spire angle. *F.*

(Chryseofusus) westralis Hadorn and Fraussen, 2003 differs by the larger shell, the wider spire angle and the smooth surface [*F. westralis* is figured as *Siphonofusus chrysodomoides* in WILSON (1994: pl. 12, figs. 7a, b)]. The two remaining small Australian species *F. consetti* (Iredale, 1929) and *F. tessellates* (Sowerby, II, 1880) are also illustrated in WILSON (194: 69, pl. 13). Both differ by their wider spire angle, the vivid colouration and by the broader and shorter siphonal canal.

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